
Effect of Items Disclosed in the GRI G4-Based Sustainability Reports on Company Value: Financial and Non-Financial Companies

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on each item and category disclosed in the latest sustainability report, namely GRI G4. The purpose of this research is to analyze and find out the effect of the disclosure of each item on the economic, social, and company categories on firm value. Given that companies are required not to pay attention to economic matters or financial performance, but further than this. The research method used is a quantitative method. The data source used is secondary data. The study population is all companies listed on the IDX. The research sample used non-probability, namely the purposive sampling method with the requirements of the company to publish successive sustainability and financial reports from 2017 to 2019 and is still actively listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). Data collection techniques use an electronic system such as PC, laptop devices, and use several website links as support. The results of this study indicate that the economic, environmental, and social categories disclosed in the sustainability report do not have a significant effect on firm value. Thus, it shows that no matter how complete the published disclosures are, the results do not have any influence on firm value.

1. INTRODUCTION

The company as an entity faces tough challenges in the current era of globalization. State boundaries become subtle or borderless which cannot be denied changing the constellation of agrarian life into industrial. The transfer of science and technology occurs so fast that it enters all aspects of life. The nation, where the majority of people lived as farmers, turned into workers in the factory industrial sector (Thompson et al. 1991). Thus it can be said that the progress of a country is influenced by matters relating to development in the industrial sector (Tobing et al. 2021). This is in accordance with Presidential Regulation No. 59 of 2017 concerning the Implementation of Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals

(TPB) further becomes the foundation for every business actor including entities to play an active role in implementing the goals of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Many phenomena occur regarding environmental damage due to industrialization. One example is the Lapindo Brantas case which was the origin of the mudflows in the Sidoarjo area (Natalia 2014). The company is the party most responsible for the damage caused by industrialization. It is undeniable that the main goal of the company is to seek profit, but a good financial condition is not enough to guarantee the company's regular growth (Abdurrasodik et al. 2020). Employees asked the company to pay more attention to their ownership rights. Investors, governments, and other parties will have different interests, but the point is that the

entity can reduce the level of risk it creates. The company then realizes the wishes of the stakeholders in the form of the CSR programs it offers. The establishment of a CSR program as a form of responsibility for the company's operational activities. The more and more useful programs provided by the company, the better stigma among stakeholders (Rosiana et al. 2013).

A sustainability report based on the definition of the Global Reporting Initiative (2014) is a report published by a company or organization regarding the economic, social, and environmental impacts caused by daily activities (which) also present values (Maskat 2018). Organization and governance model, as well as showing the relationship between synergies and commitment to a sustainable global economy. A sustainability report is a reflection of a company or organization's performance that includes economic, social, and environmental dimensions as a corporate medium to communicate its performance results to stakeholders in order to set goals, measure performance, and manage any changes in the company's operations in the corridor of sustainability (Sari et al. 2017).

Previous research on sustainability reports on company value as reflected in share value was carried out by Loh et al. (2017) to analyze the value relevance of sustainability reporting in Singapore which proves that there is a positive relationship between sustainability reporting and firm value. Ibrahim et al. (2015) show the results of their research that CSR reporting in Indonesia has a positive effect on firm value. The results are inversely proportional to the research stating that it is partially known that each sustainability report disclosure, namely economic, environmental, and social performance does not have a significant effect on firm value (Sejati and Prastiwi 2015). Purwanti et al. (2019) prove that the disclosure of sustainability reports has no effect on company value, because the costs incurred due to disclosure of sustainability reports can cause unfavorable conditions for the company. Another implication is that the level of profit earned will be smaller and have an effect on investor's decisions.

Based on the explanation of the phenomenon above, the research gap, and the supporting theory regarding sustainability reporting, the researchers are interested in conducting further research in relation to the

sustainability report with the title *The Effect of Differences in Intensity of the Number of Items Disclosed in GRI G4-Based Sustainability Reports on Firm Value (Case Study: Financial and Non-Financial Companies Listed on IDX 2017-2019)*. The novelty of this research is to use the latest edition or issue of sustainability reports, namely GRI G4, besides that the research data includes companies in all or 9 sectors listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX).

This study has several research hypotheses, namely: **H1:** The economic categories expressed in the GRI G4-based sustainability report have a positive effect on firm value. **H2:** The environmental category disclosed in the GRI G4-based sustainability report has a positive influence on firm value. **H3:** The social categories expressed in the GRI G4-based sustainability report have a positive influence on company value. The research objectives were obtained from the research hypotheses described previously: (1) to determine the effect of the economic categories expressed in the GRI G4 based sustainability report on firm value; (2) to determine the effect of environmental categories disclosed in the GRI G4 based sustainability report on firm value; (3) to determine the effect of social categories expressed in the GRI G4 based sustainability report on firm value.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory provides information that it is not only to one stakeholder that the company must be responsible, but there are several stakeholders who must also be considered by the company. This is in line with Chariri and Ghazali (2007) stating that the definition of stakeholder theory is that a company carries out its business operations not only for the company, but there are other stakeholders that the company must provide benefits such as investors, creditors, suppliers, employees, the surrounding community, and the government. To stakeholders, companies are not allowed to fulfill the needs of one party only. Furthermore, the company's responsibility is broader than just focusing on shareholders to become other stakeholders (Miqdad and Oktaviani 2021).

Signalling Theory

Spence (1978) states that signals or cues given by the sender (information owner) provide pieces of information that are relevant to users in making decisions. Brigham and Houston (2014:184) define signal theory as a company management behavior to provide investor guidance regarding the company's future prospects. The purpose of giving these signals is different depending on the person giving the signal (the information owner). If an example is a company, then this signal is a form of accountability to stakeholders, including maintaining the good name and image of the company among stakeholders (Dania et al. 2019). The information presented by the company is complete and good, indicating that the company has a good history as well. Conversely, if the presentation of information is not done completely, there are indications of things or omissions that are trying to cover up (Nisa et al. 2019).

This situation also applies when the issuance of a company's sustainability report. Stakeholders do not actually see it from a financial perspective only, but the non-financial paradigm is another important consideration. This is also in line with the company's operational activities as stipulated in Law no. 32 (2009), that it is necessary to prioritize the principles of sustainable and environmentally friendly development. This environmental performance, which is then complemented by social performance, will be disclosed in the sustainability report and will further strengthen the company's image (Gumanti et al. 2020).

Legitimacy Theory

The legitimacy theory states that organizations must pay attention to all the rights of the community, not only the rights of investors (Unerman and Deegan 2011). From this definition it is clear that each company requires adjusting the values contained and practiced in the community where the company or entity stands (Rizki et al. 2019). The problem that cannot be avoided is when a legitimacy gap occurs, where the values adopted by the company are not in line with the values held by the local community (Indriani 2018). This condition clearly affects the company's operational sustainability and its severity can lead to a conflict of legitimacy if it is not handled properly. Therefore, companies need to disclose sustainability reports using the latest

guidelines to minimize the legitimacy gap and legitimacy conflicts (Roziq et al. 2021).

Sustainability Report

The definition of a sustainability report is a form of company responsibility report regarding sustainable economic issues so that it can help companies communicate environmental and social as well as economic performance to users (Indriani 2018). The institution that was the first to pioneer sustainability reporting, namely the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) to be precise in 1997. The standards issued by GRI provide accurate guidelines for companies to implement them. The latest guideline is GRI G4 which consists of economic, social, and environmental categories with a total number of items of 91 items (Hardiyansah et al. 2021).

The Value of Company

Sujoko and Subiantoro (2007: 42) in Habibi (2017) company value is defined as a perception of investors on the success of company management, which is attributed to the stock price. The company tries to increase the value of this company as much as possible so that the main additional capital from investors can be more. Thus, company value can also be called market value, because if this value increases it will have a good influence in the form of a more secure shareholder's prosperity (Gumanti et al. 2020). There are several indicators that affect firm value, including:

1. PER (Price Earning Ratio) is a ratio that describes the share price to company earnings, or in other words how much is a reflection of the stock price obtained from company earnings (Tandelilin 2017:321).
2. PBV (Price Book Value) is a ratio that assesses the fairness of the stock price by calculating the latest share value compared to the book value of the most recent financial statements (Zubaidi 2018).
3. A measure of company value can also use the present value of the company's cash flow.
4. It can also be reflected in the profitability ratios such as ROA, ROE, ROI, NPM, and dividend policies taken and decisions on debt.

Previous Research

There are many research results that have tested the effect of sustainability report disclosure on firm value and show inconsistencies in results, such as Utami (2019) which states that disclosure of social categories affects firm value. Economic and social disclosures have an indirect effect on firm value through financial performance. The environmental and social dimensions of the sustainability report show a positive influence on company value (Pratama et al. 2020). In line with this research, CSR disclosure has a positive and significant effect on the value of manufacturing companies listed on the IDX in 2008-2012 (Rosiana et al. 2013).

Different results are shown by Sejati and Prastiwi (Sejati and Prastiwi 2015), Muallifin and Priyadi (2016) which states that sustainability reports have no effect on financial performance and firm value. The disclosure index of economic, environmental, and social performance has no effect on the value of companies in the mining sector for the 2011-2016 period (Maskat 2018).

Economic Aspects, Environmental Aspects, and Social Aspects Disclosed in GRI G4-Based Sustainability Reports Have a Positive Effect on Company Values

Based on stakeholder theory, it states that internal and external parties who influence directly and indirectly, the company is obliged to pay attention to it. Not only focusing on one party, the interests of other stakeholders are neglected (Khasanah et al. 2021). It is not enough just to manage the economic sphere or category, without paying attention to other things. In fact, it cannot be denied that when a company focuses on economic performance, automatically disclosing economic performance categories in the sustainability report will show good results so that stakeholders, especially investors, view the company as having good and profitable values (Sri Kustono 2021).

On the other hand, the number of cases caused by the company's operational activities, especially in environmental aspects, will affect the company's image which tends to be good in terms of economic performance (Winarno et al. 2021). Moreover, the issuance of Law no. 32 (Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia 2009), which contains sustainable and environmentally sound development, increasingly demands companies to heed these rules. The reputation of

the company that heed the rules regarding the environment is certainly getting better among the community (Apriono et al. 2021). Stakeholders know that today's companies do not think only about selfishness to enrich themselves, but far more than that the company also pays attention to the circumstances of the surrounding environment (Hardiyansah et al. 2021). Thus, the company's competitive advantage can be created and this will make the company's value more and more viewed by stakeholders.

Apart from environmental interests, the company has contractual ties with the community because the output will be offered to the community. Astuti and Juwenah (2017) and Maskat (Maskat 2018) disclosure of the economic performance index has a positive and significant effect on firm value. Kusuma and Priantinah (2018) prove that the disclosure of the environmental dimension sustainability report has an effect on firm value. Puspitandari and Septiani (2017) disclosure of sustainability report, social dimensions have a positive effect on company value.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The type of Research

This study the author uses a quantitative type, because it emphasizes theory testing through measurement of research variables in the form of numbers and then analyzed using the help of statistical tools, namely SPSS (Indriantoro and Supomo 2009:12).

Population

Population is a group of people, events, or everything with their respective characteristics (Indriantoro and Supomo 2009). The population of this research is financial and non-financial companies listed on the IDX for the 2017-2019 period.

Sample

The sample is part or elements of the number and characteristics possessed by the population or in other words, this sample is part of the population (Sugiyono 2011:181). The research sample was selected using purposive sampling method, with the following criteria: (1) Financial and non-financial companies that publish financial reports or annual reports for the 2017-2019 period. (2) Companies that publish sustainable reports use the latest GRI G4

guidelines for two consecutive years, 2017-2019.
(3) Companies that are active in stock trading activities.

The Type and Source of Data

The data source in this study is secondary data, namely in the form of a GRI G4-based sustainability report published by the company during the 2017-2019 time period. Indriantoro and Supomo (Indriantoro and Supomo 2009) secondary data is a type of data obtained indirectly, namely using intermediary media (obtained from other parties). The data source in the form of a sustainability report is obtained from the company's website or other credible and trusted website.

Method of Collecting Data

This research data collection method uses documentation by looking directly for GRI G4-based sustainability reports and annual financial reports of financial and non-financial companies for the period 2017-2019. In addition, literature studies use books, journals, articles, and other sources that support this research topic.

Research Variable

In this research there are 2 types of variables, independent variable and dependent variable. (1) Independent Variable In this study, the independent variable used was the sustainability report item based on GRI G4 (X1). (2) Dependent Variable In this study, the dependent variable used is firm value (Y).

The Explanation of Operational Variables

operational variables explain the determination of constructs so that they become measurable variable forms (Indriantoro and Supomo 2009). The operational definitions of the research variables are:

Sustainability Report if the company discloses each category item, it is given a score of 1 and if it does not disclose a score of 0. The following is the SRDI calculation formula:

$$SRDI = \frac{K}{N}$$

Information:

SRDI = Sustainability Report Disclosure Index
K = Number of items disclosed
N = Number of items that should be disclosed

Economy Category the formula for calculating the disclosure of economic categories, or

Economic Disclosure Index (EcDI) (Sejati and Prastiwi 2015):

$$EcDI = \text{---}$$

Environment Category the formula for calculating the disclosure of economic categories, or Environment Disclosure Index (EnDI) (Sejati and Prastiwi 2015):

$$EnDI = \text{---}$$

Social Category the calculation formula for social category disclosure, or Social Disclosure Index (SoDI) (Sejati and Prastiwi 2015):

$$SoDI = \text{---}$$

The Value of Company the proxy for firm value in this study uses the Price Earning Ratio (PER). The calculation of Price Earning Ratio (PER) is as follows (Tandelilin 2017):

$$PER = \frac{\text{Price of Share}}{EPS}$$

$$EPS = \frac{\text{Earning After Tax}}{\text{The Amount of Share Outstanding}}$$

Data Anlysis Method

In this study, the data analysis method used the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) Version 23.

Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics are defined as the process of transforming data into tabulated form, namely in the form of summaries and compilation of data in graphical and numeric tables with the aim of facilitating understanding and implementation for readers.

Classic Assumption Test

Before testing the research hypothesis, first testing the classical assumptions to determine the feasibility of using the research model (Maskat 2018). It is further explained by Ghozali (Ghozali 2011) that the classical assumptions that are considered important are: a. There are no symptoms of multicollinearity between the independent variables. b. Free from the constant confounding variable variants or in other words there is no heteroscedasticity. c. Overall data is normally distributed.

Normality Test

Normality testing is carried out to determine the residual results of the regression model whether the data is normally distributed or not. Researchers can see in the P-Plot image, if the plotting data (points) of the test results

follow a diagonal line, the data is normally distributed. In addition, to ensure that you can also look at the column or Kolmogorov Smirnov one sample test using a significant level of 5% and look at the asymp sig.2 tailed. If the 2 tailed results are more than 0.05, it is said that the data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Ghozali (Ghozali 2011) multicollinearity testing was carried out with the aim of knowing the correlation shown by the independent variable. Researchers can see the tolerance and VIF values of the independent variables, if the data is symptom free of multicollinearity, the condition is $VIF < 10$ and the tolerance value > 0.10 .

Heteroscedasticity Test

The purpose of this test is to determine the residual variance inequality from one observation to another in the regression model. Researchers can observe the scatterplot, if there is no clear pattern (wavy, widened then narrowed) in the scatterplots image, as well as the dots spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis (Ghozali 2011). In addition, there are other tests, namely Glejser test, white test, and Park test to determine whether there is heteroscedasticity or not.

Autocorrelation Test

The purpose of this test is to determine whether there is a correlation between the disturbing error in period n and the disturbing error in period n-1. Researchers can test durbin Watson, namely Ghozali (Ghozali 2011), there is no autocorrelation symptom, if the Durbin Watson value is between du to (4-du).

Multiple Linier Regression Test

Linear regression analysis was carried out aimed at testing and measuring the effect of one independent variable on the dependent variable. The study used multiple regression analysis model analysis with several variables, namely the economic category, environmental category, and social category served in the sustainability report. The regression equation for the research hypothesis is shown by:
 $Y = \alpha + \beta_1 EcDI + \beta_2 EnDI + \beta_3 SoDI + e.$

Coefficient of Determination

Researchers can read the coefficient of determination to measure the extent to which the

research model explains the dependent variable. The value of Adjusted R Square shows that the level of confidence in the resulting data is influenced by the dependent variable (X) and other variables.

F test

The F test is a test that must be carried out in conducting linear regression analysis with the aim of seeing whether the regression model has met the criteria or not. F Test Criteria (Ghozali 2011):

1. If $F_{count} > F_{table}$ it is concluded that the independent variable affects the dependent variable.
2. If $F_{count} < F_{table}$, it is concluded that the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable.

Researchers can also see from the output with the following criteria:

1. If the significance value is less than 0.05, variable X affects variable Y.
2. If the significance value is more than 0.05, then variable X has no effect on variable Y.

Test T Test

The T test is carried out with the aim of knowing the partial influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable, namely Y which is considered a fixed value. This influence can be seen from the sig column coefficients table. then compared between T table with T count.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1. The Results of Statistics Descriptive

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
SRDI_Ekonomi	41	,00	7,00	3,0976	1,70007
SRDI_Lingkungan	41	,00	15,00	6,9756	3,83724
SRDI_Sosial	41	1,00	24,00	10,1220	5,39535
NILAI PERUSAHAAN_PE R	41	,02471	3,19951	1,2808785	,87640176
Valid N (listwise)	41				

Sources : Output of SPSS

Based on data processing shown in the table above, it can be seen that the SRDI_Ekonomi variable has a minimum value of 0.00, a maximum value of 7.00 with an average of 3.0976, and a standard deviation of

1.70007. The SRDI_Lingkungan variable has a minimum value of 0.00, a maximum value of 15.00 with an average of 6.9756, and a standard deviation of 3.83724. The SRDI_Sosial variable has a minimum value of 1.00, a maximum value of 24.00 with a mean of 10.1220, and a standard deviation of 0.87640176.

Normality Test

Table 2. The Results of One Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		41
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	,81876367
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,127
	Positive	,127
	Negative	-,088
Test Statistic		,127
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,096 ^c

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

Source : Output of SPSS

The results of normality testing using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov table show the sig value. $0.096 > 0.05$, so that referring to Ghozali (Ghozali 2011) data is normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 3. The Results of Muticollinearity Test

Variable	Collinearity Statistic		Desc.
	Tolerance	VIF	
SRDI_Ekonomi	0,619	1,616	Passed Multikol Test
SRDI_Lingk.	0,834	1,199	Passed Multikol Test
SRDI_Sosial	0,548	1,824	Passed Multikol Test

Source : Processed by Author

Based on the test shown in the table above, it shows that all variables have a tolerance value > 0.10 and a VIF value < 10 , so that referring to Ghozali (Ghozali 2011), the data does not have multicollinearity symptoms.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 4. The Results of Heteroscedasticity Test

Source : Output of SPSS

Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test, it is known that there is no pattern (dots) meaning that the points spread above and below the Y axis 0 number. Thus referring to Ghozali (Ghozali 2011) there is no heteroscedasticity symptom.

Autocorrelation Test

Table 5. The Results of Autocorrelation Test

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,357 ^a	,127	,056	,85130993	2,054

- a. Predictors: (Constant), SRDI_Sosial, SRDI_Lingkungan, SRDI_Ekonomi
- b. Dependent Variable: NILAIPERUSAHAAN_PER

Source : Output of SPSS

Based on the results of the autocorrelation test, it was found that the results of $du = 1.6603$ durbin watson = 2.054, and $4-du = 2.3397$ so that the durbin watson value is located between du and $4-du$, and there is no autocorrelation (Ghozali 2011).

Multiple Linier Regression Test

R² Test

Table 6. The Results of R² Test

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,357 ^a	,127	,056	,85130993	2,054

- a. Predictors: (Constant), SRDI_Sosial, SRDI_Lingkungan, SRDI_Ekonomi
- b. Dependent Variable: NILAIPERUSAHAAN_PER

Source : Output of SPSS

Based on the test results above, it can be seen that the value of R Square is only 0.056, which means that the dependent variable being

tested is that the company value is influenced by the independent variable, namely the disclosure of economic, environmental, and social categories, only around 5.6%, while 94.4% is influenced by variables. another. In addition, it can also be seen that the standard error value in this test is 0.85130993.

T Test

Table 7. The Results of T Test

Variable	Count of T	Table T
SRDI_Ekonomi	0,848	2,01954
SRDI_Lingk.	-1,147	2,01954
SRDI_Sosial	-1,466	2,01954

Source : Processed by Author

Based on the test results using the T test, it was found that the economic disclosure variable of the sustainability report based on GRI G4 in financial and non-financial sector companies for the 2017-2019 period was 0.848 < 2.01954 so that it had no effect on firm value and the first hypothesis was rejected. In addition, the environmental disclosure variable for the sustainability report based on GRI G4 in financial and non-financial sector companies for the 2017-2019 period is -1.147 < 2.01954 so that it has no effect on firm value and the second hypothesis is rejected. Furthermore, the GRI G4 based social sustainability report disclosure variable in financial and non-financial sector companies for the 2017-2019 period is -1.466 < 2.01954 so that it has no effect on firm value and the third hypothesis is rejected.

F Test

Table 8. The Results of F Test

Model	Count of F	Table F
Regression	1,798	2,85

Source : Processed by Author

Based on the test results above, it was found that the value of F calculated was 1.798 < F table 2.85 so that the overall disclosure of economic, social, and environmental sustainability reports on financial and non-financial companies for the 2017-2019 period had no effect on company value.

Testing using the Price Earning Ratio (PER) proxy does not have a significant effect and impact on companies that have published their sustainability reports. The true value of the company will be used by investors in making investment decisions. Investors and other stakeholders consider that the disclosure of each item in the 3 categories of sustainability reports is not a meaningful thing, meaning that it is only additional information and stakeholders are still not too aware other than the financial statements issued by the company. Furthermore, stakeholders prefer real action by the company without involving disclosure in the form of a report, because it could be that the report is only made for the sake of increasing popularity and in fact this action has not been carried out. This is in line with several studies conducted by Sejati and Prastiwi (Sejati and Prastiwi 2015), Maskat (Maskat 2018) which states that the more complete or not the company in disclosing the performance of the three existing categories does not make the company's value better.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

This study comes as a follow-up to the inconsistencies of several previous studies. The test results using SPSS show that the variable disclosure of economic, social, and environmental categories of sustainability reports based on GRI G4 has no effect on firm value using the Price Earning Ratio (PER) proxy.

The limitation of this study is that there is an indication of the element of subjectivity in assigning value to items disclosed in the sustainability report and many other variables that affect the value of the company have not been explored in research, apart from sustainability reports.

Research suggestions that can be given are that the next researcher can use techniques or methods to minimize the subjectivity of researchers in assessing each item disclosed, for example with the help of certain tools and exploring other variables such as company performance and good governance practices or other variables that can also influence. to company value.

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